

Additional Materials

Paper: Process Mining Practices: Evidence from Interviews

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In this document we provide details about the conduct of our interview study following the empirical standard for interview studies available online on:

<https://github.com/acmsigsoft/EmpiricalStandards/blob/master/docs/QualitativeSurveys.md#myfootnote1>

Since the interview was part of a broader observational study, we would like to note that considerations about the participants' selection and data analysis hold for the complete study.

Participants' Selection

Inclusion Criteria

Our goal is to gain an understanding of process mining practices, with a focus on strategies of the *Mining & Analysis* stage, as captured by our research question: **What are the common strategies used in the analysis stage?** Since in the *Mining & Analysis* stage (van Eck, 2015) process mining techniques are applied to event logs to answer a research question, we targeted participants familiar with event log analysis.

To this end, we defined the following requirements for participation:

1. Having analyzed at least two real-life event logs over the two years prior to the study,
2. Being knowledgeable of at least one among bupaR, Celonis, Disco, pm4py, ProM, i.e., the process mining tools available for the process mining task.

Besides, for this interview study, we considered participants with experience in process mining projects having the main goal to analyze process data for a customer to ensure that they had gained sufficient practical experience with event log analysis.

Such requirements allowed us to exclude beginners from our population of interest but still include participants with different backgrounds (e.g., academics vs. practitioners) and varying levels of experience and expertise, which are needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of analysis strategies. In this way, we can potentially identify different strategies for different participants' groups and to discern between effective and not effective strategies.

Sampling Strategy

For our study, we aimed to collect between 30 and 50 participants, based on the guidelines in (Mason, 2010) for qualitative studies and interviews.

Initially, we made a list of potential participants with the help of our project partners selecting from our professional networks people that we thought met the participation requirements and had not participated in our previous pilot study (Zerbato, 2021). At this stage, we avoided putting in the list people affiliated with the same institution or company, and we tried to balance academics and practitioners.

Then, we invited participants by reaching out to them via email. In the invitation email, we described the purpose of the study, the requirements for participation, the setup, the kinds of data collected, and an estimate of the time effort needed for the whole session.

Overall, we sent out 48 invitations between May and June 2021. 40 invitees replied to our invitation (83.3% response rate), and 30 agreed to participate in the study (62.5% acceptance rate). The reasons for declining were not meeting the participation requirements (5 invitees) or time/job constraints (3 people). While collecting the data, five participants with large professional networks offered to put us in touch with peers potentially interested in participating in our study. With their help, we invited 30 additional participants to our study. 17 invitees replied to our invitation (56.7% response rate), and 11 agreed to participate in the study (36.6% acceptance rate). Again, the reasons for declining were not meeting the participation requirements (6 people) and time constraints (1 person).

Our sampling strategy allowed us to include participants working as academics or practitioners in the process mining field and meeting the minimum requirements for participation. At the same time, since the requirements for participation are rather broad, we tried to balance participants based on their affiliation (academics vs practitioners and different company or university), job role and position (junior/senior roles) and tool knowledge. Recruiting additional participants with the help of five participants allowed us to include in our sample users of all the five process mining tools available for the task.

Saturation

We stopped collecting data when we achieved data saturation (Saunders, 2018), i.e., we noticed that answers were repeating across interviews and that patterns in the work practices were starting to emerge.

Examples.

The two statements below remark that without domain knowledge there is a risk to conduct analyses that are trivial or not interesting.

«I mean, we are typically as researchers, not the domain experts. So you tend to come up with trivial things or you you don't have a clear goal in mind.» (p18)

«... I understand a lot of the of the business process with business people and it avoids me to to ask me silly questions or to put down silly hypotheses.» (p34)

The two statements below remark that stakeholders have a feeling of critical steps and the analysis can quickly focus on such steps.

«...the subject matter experts at the customers say they do know already or have a very good god feeling about what might be wrong. So, we can, we can very quickly dig into that.» (p11)

“Sometimes people already have the feeling that some process steps are really inefficient and say we have to focus there» (p23)

The two statements below refer to the focus on anomalies.

«So, I do a lot of outlier detection, unsupervised learning to find clusters of anomalies, outliers, etc...» (p25)

«But then in general, I think that something that is rather universal in all event logs would be to check for anomalous cases» (p36)

Participants' Details

Data Validation

Overall, 41 people participated in our study. On average, we collected 83 minutes of recordings per participant, which we fully transcribed verbatim. From our analysis, we excluded four participants. Two participants did not conduct the task prior to the interview for personal and technical reasons. Two others did not have project experience with process mining projects aimed to analyze process data for a customer, which we considered relevant to our research question. Thus, in this paper, we focus on the interviews of the 37 remaining participants (20 practitioners and 17 academics from 29 different organizations), lasting 1136 minutes in total and 31 minutes on average.

Demographics

We collected demographic characteristics and self-reported experience and expertise in process mining and related fields through a demographic questionnaire. A summary of the collected information for the 37 participants selected for the interview study is shown in **Table 1**.

P#	Sector	Current Role	Experience (yrs)		Expertise		#Projects	#Tools	#Logs
			Process Mining	Data Science	Process Mining	Process Analytics			
1	Enterprise Software	Product Manager	2	Up to 1	Good	Basic	1	1	2 - 5
2	Academia	PhD Student	1	1-3	Average	Average	1	3	6 - 10
3	National Laboratory	Senior R&D Staff	3	> 10	Good	Average	2 - 5	2	> 10
4	Consulting	Senior R&D Staff	2	6-10	Average	Average	1	3	2 - 5
5	Consumer Goods	Process Analyst	2.5	Up to 1	Average	Average	2 - 5	1	6 - 10
6	Frelance	Process Mining Consultant	2	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
7	Academia	Professor	10	6-10	Advanced	Average	6 - 10	3	> 10
8	Academia	Assistant Professor	10	4-5	Advanced	Good	2 - 5	2	> 10
9	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	3.5	1-3	Good	Good	> 20	2	6 - 10
11	Freelance	Business Analyst	8	> 10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	6 - 10
12	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Good	2 - 5	4	2 - 5
13	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	1	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1	2 - 5
14	Enterprise Software	Product Manager/Engineer	3	1-3	Good	Good	10 - 20	1	> 10
15	Academia	Assistant Professor	6	6-10	Good	Average	2 - 5	3	> 10
16	Academia	PhD Student	4	None	Average	Average	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
17	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	4	1-3	Good	Average	10 - 20	1	> 10
18	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	> 10
19	Academia	Assistant Professor	8	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	4	> 10
20	Enterprise Software	Partner Relationships Manager	0.3	Up to 1	Basic	Basic	1	1	2 - 5
22	Academia	Graduate Student	0.3	1-3	Basic	Basic	1	1	2 - 5
23	Enterprise Software	Process Mining Consultant	1	Up to 1	Average	Average	2 - 5	2	2 - 5
24	Enterprise Software	Analytics Product Management	3	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	1	6 - 10
25	Food Processing	Process Analyst	4	> 10	Good	Good	2 - 5	2	6 - 10
26	Packaging	Digital Project Manager	7	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	1	2 - 5
27	Financial	Process Mining Analyst	1	1-3	Average	Average	2 - 5	5	6 - 10
28	Academia	Professor	4	> 10	Good	Good	2 - 5	4	> 10
29	Academia	PhD Student	6	6-10	Good	Average	2 - 5	5	> 10
30	Academia	Professor	10	1-3	Average	Good	2 - 5	5	2 - 5
31	Telecommunications	Principal Business Consultant	2	> 10	Basic	Good	2 - 5	1	> 10
32	Academia	PhD Student	2	1-3	Average	Basic	2 - 5	2	2 - 5
33	Constructions	Operational Excellence Lead	3	4-5	Advanced	Advanced	6 - 10	1	> 10
34	Government	Consultant	10	> 10	Good	Good	6 - 10	2	2 - 5
36	Academia	PhD Student	6	1-3	Good	Good	2 - 5	3	6 - 10
37	Insurance	Operational Excellence Lead	5	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	> 20	1	> 10
38	Academia	Professor	8	4-5	Good	Good	6 - 10	4	6 - 10
39	Academia	Senior Researcher	7	6-10	Advanced	Advanced	10 - 20	5	2 - 5
41	Academia	PhD Student	7	6-10	Good	Advanced	2 - 5	2	6 - 10

Table 1: Overview of the 37 selected participants.

P#: is the original participant ID assigned during the data collection (P10, P21, P35, and P40 were excluded). **Sector:** the sector to which the participant's affiliation/company belongs. **Current Role:** the participant's job role at the time of the data collection. **Experience (yrs):** years of experience in process mining and data science or analytics. **Expertise:** expertise in process mining and process analytics; a Likert scale with values Novice, Basic, Average, Good and Advanced was used. **#Projects:** the number of process mining having the goal of analyzing process data for a customer/company. **#Tools:** the number of process mining tools that the participant

can use comfortably. **#Logs**: the number of event logs analyzed in the past two years. **#Projects** was used as an additional filter to ensure a sufficient level of expertise with analysis projects. **#Tools** and **#Logs** are related to our participation requirements.

Interviewer Experience and Perspective

The interviewer has 6 years of experience in the BPM field, including 2 years in the process mining area. Prior to this study, the interviewer had experience with designing and conducting one interview study involving 14 participants, two pilot interview studies involving 3 participants, and two follow-up interviews part of experiments involving more than 20 participants. The interviewer adopted a research perspective that mainly focused on understanding process mining practices and typical actions and strategies.

Interview Guide

(T): To be asked referring to the process mining task (G): To be asked referring to general work practices

ACTIVITIES, TARGET ARTIFACTS and USE of ARTIFACTS

- Can you briefly summarize the main steps of your analysis today and explain why you worked in this way? (T)
- Would you always follow the same steps in practice? (G)
- What information did you aim to gather during the analysis? Why? (T)
- Would you always focus on gathering the same information in practice or does that change from case to case? (G)
- How did you use the provided artifacts during the analysis? Why were they useful? (T)

GOALS

- Can you summarize the main goals of your analysis today? (T)
- Do you always work with these goals in mind in practice? (G)
- Do you always have clear analysis goals or objectives in practice? (G)
- On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that the analyses you conduct in practice are exploratory? By exploratory we mean that you spend time refining research questions, generating new questions for the analysis.

STRATEGIES, START and TERMINATION CRITERIA

- Did you follow any specific strategy (plan of action to achieve a certain goal) when trying to answer the questions today? (T)
- Did your analysis approach change during the analysis? If so, how? (T)
- Would you follow the same approach in practice, with other event logs? (G)
- How did you decide where to start your analysis from? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually choose where to start your analysis from? (G)
- How did you decide that it was time to stop the analysis? Did you follow any criteria? (T)
- In practice, how do you usually decide that it is time to stop the analysis? (G)

CHALLENGES

- Is there anything that you found challenging during the task today? (T)
 - And in general, what do you think are the biggest challenges of process mining? (G)
 - On a scale from 1 to 10, how much do you think that good tool knowledge helps to overcome process mining challenges? (G)
 - Do you think that combining different process mining tools is an opportunity for the analysis or do you think it is too complicated/not needed? (G)
 - Taking a look at process mining, where do you think there is more need for methodological or operational support? (G)
-

Chain of Evidence from Interviewee Quotations to Findings

The coding process is described in **Section 3**, paragraph *Data Validation and Analysis*. More details on the three coding rounds are provided in an Excel file on:

<https://drive.switch.ch/index.php/s/n7SBxlsveD4ggIM>

Findings

The findings of our paper that respond to the research question are outlined in **Section 4.1** and **Section 4.2**.

Limitations and Threats to Validity

We discuss the limitations and possible biases in **Section 5** of the paper.

References

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